

The Coupling Constants Series – Gauge Fields Prediction – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By analyzing the right term multiplier in the primordial coupling constants infinite series, there exist an interesting agreement with the number of gauge fields mediating each interacting. The author predict that there will be five distinct gauge fields mediating the third coupling term, i.e. electro magnetism.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

We also know that there are eight gluon fields. These are mediating the strong interaction and color charge. However, this could be just a coincidence. Let us examine the next term in the series:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3$$

This term describe the nature of the weak interaction. Notice the right inside the parenthesis:

$$(8 * 3)$$

We also know that there are three gauge fields meditating the weak interaction. the massive W the Z bosons. Which we correlate to $SU(2)$ and Isospin. If the right term inside the parenthesis is a reflection on the number of fields meditating an interaction than we can examine the next term on the series, electromagnetism:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5$$

That is a daring statement to make, but if the assumption to hold true, There Should be five gauge fields meditating the electric interaction. Five distinct Kinds of photons. It is really an absurd statement to make, given the fact that there are no indication that there is an agreement with experiment regarding that idea. But sometimes in Theoretical physics, bold risks must be taken, and so the author of this paper will allow his belief regarding the great power of the equation to guide him and State: **The 8-theory predicts five gauge fields meditating electromagnetism.** Whether such thing could be correct, only time and experiment will tell.

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)